

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15748944

Peer Relations As A Predictor Of Aggressive Behaviours Among In-School Adolescents In Anambra State.

*Okoyezu Vivian Ukamaka & Prof. Obikeze J. Nnamdi

Department of Educational Foundations,
Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Anambra State, Nigeria
*E-mail: vivianlinus20@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The study examined the predictive value of peer relations on aggressive behaviours of in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The study was guided by two research questions and two null hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance. The literature was reviewed under the following sub-headings; conceptual, theoretical, empirical studies and summary of literature reviewed. The study adopted correlational research design. Population of the students comprised 20,560 SSII in-school adolescents in 267 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The sample of the study consisted of 347 students drawn using Taro Yamane formular. Multistage sampling technique was used to draw the sample. Index of Peer Relations scale (IPR) and Aggression Questionnaire (AQ) were adapted as instruments for data collection. The instruments were subjected to face and content validation. The reliability of the instruments were established using Cronbach Alpha. The computation yielded coefficient values of 0.77, and 0.82 for IPR and AQ respectively. The researcher administered the instruments to the respondents with the help of six research assistants. Simple regression was used to answer research questions 1 and 2 and tested hypotheses 1 and 2. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that peer relations has a modest positive predictive value ($\beta = 0.24$, $t = 4.52$, $p = 0.000$), on aggressive behaviours. The findings also showed that peer relations has modest positive predictive value ($\beta = 0.18$, $t=2.38$, $p = 0.018$)($\beta = 0.28$, $t=3.86$, $p = 0.000$) on aggressive behaviours of male and female adolescents with more variance among females compared to the male students. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that Educational Psychologists and school administrators should provide opportunities to counselling services and support groups for adolescents struggling with aggression or peer relationship issues as well as training on life skills, such as conflict resolution, communication, and problem-solving.

Keywords: Peer Relations, Aggressive Behaviours, Gender and In-school Adolescents.

INTRODUCTION

Education is the cornerstone of human development and societal progress. It serves as a tool for personal and societal advancement, equipping students with the knowledge, skills, and values necessary to navigate life successfully. Schools are designed to be spaces where students feel safe, respected, and supported. The Nigerian educational system, guided by policy objectives, aims to raise the quality of education and position it as a driver of national development (Ugochukwu et al., 2021). However, the persistent prevalence of aggressive behaviours undermines these goals. Instead of being sanctuaries of safety and growth, schools have become arenas for hostility, particularly aggression, which significantly

compromise the quality of education and the safety of school environments with many students facing intimidation and violence, often leading to absenteeism, fear, and academic underperformance.

Aggressive behaviour is a range of actions or attitudes that are intended to cause harm, discomfort or intimidation to others. It also includes behaviour aimed at achieving dominance, control or retaliation in response to perceived threats or frustrations. In their view, Peng et al (2018) referred to aggressive behaviour as hostile actions intended to hurt someone or establish dominance. For the purpose of this study, aggressive behaviour is described by the researcher as actions that are intended to cause harm or injury to another person, either physically or psychologically. This includes a wide range of behaviours, from overt physical acts such as hitting, kicking, or pushing, to more covert psychological acts like yelling, insults, social exclusion, use of harsh language, or spreading rumors. It is characterized by the deliberate desire to inflict harm or discomfort on the target.

Aggressive behaviour is a complex topic that encompasses various forms of assertiveness and hostility. Shekarey et al, (2020) contended that aggressive behaviours are common in secondary schools and aggressive behaviour among the students is an issue of concern among stakeholders in education essentially because schools are institutions designed for teaching and learning. Aggressive behaviours among in-school adolescents can be categorized into four groups namely, physical, verbal, relational and cyberbullying (Rigby, 2018). Physical aggression is hostile form of aggression. Its aim is to cause bodily damage. It includes kicking, pushing, shoving, fighting, hitting, slapping, among others. Verbal aggression involves the use of words to hurt or threaten others. It includes name-calling, teasing or making derogatory comments. Relational aggression involves harming others through damage to relationships or social status. It can include spreading rumours, excluding others from social activities, or manipulating friendships. Cyberbullying involves using digital space or technologies, such as social media or text messaging to harm or threaten others. This behaviour is very complicated with a variety of multidimensional causes such as exposure to aggressive role model, frustrations, negative social relations with peers and teachers at school, peer pressure, low self-esteem among others. However, Amuda-Kannike (2018) revealed that biological factors can cause aggressive behaviours among secondary school students. These factors are brain dysfunction (poor functioning of the frontal and temporal region of the brain), birth complications, nutrition deficiency, genetics, stress and drug abuse.

Aggressive behaviours can cause many negative impact for the victim as well as the perpetrator. Kuar and Kuar (2020) noted that students who are victims of aggressive behaviour experience depression, low self-esteem, anxiety, stress, headache, sleep difficulties, problems meeting school's academic demands and the desire to skip school. Furthermore, UNESCO (2021) acknowledged that aggressive behaviour had an impact on the ability of students to get to and from school, to learn effectively while in school, to remain in school long enough to reap the benefits of education, and in extreme cases, school aggression may result in death. Aggressive behaviour is also related to psychopathology, and are also manifested by adolescents in secondary schools (Genovese et al 2017). This behaviour and its associated psychiatric disorders can occur throughout a person's lifespan, from childhood to adolescent, adulthood, and the elderly. If these habits remain untreated, they may progress to more detrimental psychological problems including post-traumatic stress disorder, anxiety and depression, (Manchia & Fanos 2017).

The prevalence of aggressive behaviours in the form of bullying in schools has become more prominent in the last few years, as news, articles about aggressive behaviour within the school setting is now on the increase (APA 2021). On their part, Obikeze and Obi (2020) stressed how this ugly development has adversely affected the academic performance of the students and their overall wellbeing, and how students continued involvement in aggressive behaviour has brought miseries and anguish to many parents, teachers, psychologists, guidance counsellors and the government despite many strategies put in place to curb it, the problem persists. Therefore, the mantra that school is perceived to be a place where students should feel safe and secure is no longer valid and the reality is that significant number of students are the target of aggressive acts. Therefore, it becomes necessary to explore some factors that may predict the behaviour of the perpetrators of aggressive behaviours in schools. Although aggressive behaviour is a widespread phenomenon, the focus of this study is to determine whether a relationship exists between

peer relations and aggressive behaviour. In other words, could peer relationships predict aggressive behaviours among in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Research on the causes of aggressive behaviour are focused on social learning, modeling, structural and functional brain abnormalities, hormones, and neurotransmitters. A systematic review of psychosocial predictors of adolescent aggressive behaviour showed that personality traits, emotional problems, lack of empathy, peer influence, and substance use were among the highest reported predictors, (Fatimah et al, 2019). Studies have also highlighted and focused on adolescent crisis, and environmental related factors such as peer relations, parental style, family relations, child abuse, Tv violence, gender, just but a few. This study however, elected and aligned with these set of researchers and investigated the relationship between peer relationship and aggressive behaviours of in-school adolescents in Anambra State. In – school adolescents typically refers to young individuals who are currently enrolled in an educational institution, such as a school or college. These adolescents are actively participating in academic programs and are typically between the ages of 10 to 19 years old. The term is often used in discussions related to education, health, and social services to specifically target interventions or programs designed to support this demographic group. By examining the correlation between peer relations and aggressive behaviours, this study sought to provide valuable insights into the intricate web of influences shaping adolescent behaviour in this specific Nigerian context.

Relationship with peers are of central importance to children throughout childhood and adolescence. Peer relations is the interactions and relationships that occur between individuals of similar age, typically within an educational or social context, which play a crucial role in social and emotional development (Rubin et al, 2015). These relationships help individuals learn social skills, develop a sense of identity, and provide emotional support. Shao and Kang (2022) defined peer relations as a kind of interpersonal relationship developed in the process of interaction in small clusters of individuals that are closely connected with each other based on shared interests and friendships. From the foregoing, the researcher defines peer relations as the interactions and social connections between individuals of similar age or status within a particular setting, such as a school, workplace or community.

Peer relations play a pivotal role in adolescent's lives, serving as a primary context for socialization and identity formation. It encourages adolescents to develop independence from their parents by forming their own social networks through which they learn essential social skills and gain emotional well-being (Shao & Kang, 2022). Peers with supportive relationships provide each other emotional stability which allows them to learn social skills, develop empathy, which are essential for emotional well-being and adjustment (Seban et al, 2016). Furthermore, Zhang and Chen (2018), affirmed that strong and supportive relationships provide adolescents with a sense of belonging, acceptance, and emotional support. Positive peer relations can provide support, companionship, and opportunities for learning and growth (Wentzel, 2017). However, Adolescents who experience peer relationship difficulties are at high risk of emotional and psychological problems including aggressive behaviours, low self-esteem, delinquency, and poor adaptation in school, bullying, social isolation, excessive alcohol consumption and drug use (Powers et al, as cited in Kim & Nho, 2017). Peer and school adaptation, accordingly, is a significant aspect in adolescents' life. Generally, the importance of peer relationships further increases in adolescence as they spend about one third of their waking hours with peers, which is approximately twice the time they spend with their parents or other adults (Gungor et al, 2021).

Furthermore, gender differences add another layer of complexity to understanding adolescent aggression. There is ongoing debate surrounding whether aggressive behaviour exhibited by girls differs significantly from or resembles that of boys in similar circumstances. Research suggests a complex relationship between gender and aggressive behaviour in adolescents. Research in gender differences showed that male students scored significantly higher in different dimensions of aggressive behaviours such as physical, verbal, anger and hostility than female students (Afusat, 2024). On the other hand, Snoban and Kumar (2016) contended that female students exhibited more aggressive behaviours than male students.

Although a good number of researchers like Wakolia et al, (2016) examined peer relations on aggressive behaviours of adolescents in secondary schools in Bungoma County, the problem of aggressive behaviours among in-school adolescents seems to persist and remain a source of worry and concern to

many researchers. This has necessitated this study which sought to investigate peer relations as a predictor of aggressive behaviours among in-school adolescents in Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

Aggressive behaviours among in-school adolescents is an issue of concern among stakeholders in education essentially because schools are institutions designed for teaching and learning. Unarguably, teaching and learning can only successfully take place in a conducive environment devoid of intimidations, harassment, insecurity and fear.

However, the researcher observed that most secondary school students in Anambra State seem to indulge in various forms of aggressive behaviours such as pushing, fighting, teasing, verbal humiliation, slapping, kicking, bullying, name calling, restiveness, physical confrontations, knife attacks among others. Therefore, the mantra that school is perceived to be a place where students should feel safe and secure is no longer valid and the reality is that significant number of students are the target of aggressive acts. Aggressive behaviours can have negative significant impact on teaching and learning, social relationships and overall well-being. Additionally, it can create a negative learning environment making it challenging for students to focus and succeed academically. Furthermore, aggressive behaviours can contribute to increased stress, anxiety levels, depression, and low self-concept among others.

Addressing Students' aggressive behaviour earlier through developing effective coping strategies is crucial to mitigate these negative effects. This has necessitated this study which sought to investigate peer relations as a predictor of aggressive behaviours among in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra State using gender as moderating variable.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine peer relations as a predictor of aggressive behaviours among in-school adolescents in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the predictive value of Peer relations on aggressive behaviour of SSII in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Determine the predictive value of Peer relations on aggressive behaviour of male and female SSII in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Significance of the Study

The findings of the study would be of great significance to students, teachers, psychologists, guidance counsellors, policy makers and future researchers.

The findings of the study would help students gain insights into how peer relations impact on their behaviour. Understanding these would help them reflect on their actions and adopt non-aggressive ways of interacting with other students.

The findings of this study would equip teachers with the knowledge to identify warning signs of aggressive behaviours stemming from peers. This would help teachers to design strategies to reduce aggressive behaviours among students.

The findings of this study would help psychologists uncover how peer relations can contribute to aggressive behaviours. This would enable them design effective interventions targeting specific causes of aggressive behaviours such as addressing negative peer interactions and teaching students to navigate peer pressure.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the predictive value of Peer relations on aggressive behaviour of SSII in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What is the predictive value of Peer relations on aggressive behaviour of male and female SSII in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Peer relations would not significantly predict aggressive behaviour of SSII in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra state.

2. Peer relations would not significantly predict aggressive behaviour of male and female SSII in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra state.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Correlational research design was adopted for this study.

Area of the Study

The research was carried out among in-school adolescents in Anambra State, Nigeria. The people of the state are predominantly traders, farmers, civil servants, and entrepreneurs. Anambra State has six education zones namely Aguata, Awka, Nnewi, Onitsha, Ogidi, and Otuocha with 267 public secondary schools.

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised 20,560 in-school adolescents from senior secondary two (SS2) students (8,775 males and 10,775 females) in the 267 public secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Anambra State (Planning Research and Statistics Department, Post Primary Schools Service Commission (PPSSC), Anambra State Awka, 2023).

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample for the study was 392 SS2 students drawn from the population of the study. Multistage sampling technique was used for sample size selection. First, three schools were randomly selected from each of the six Education Zones for good representation, making a total of 18 schools. Within each selected school, students were stratified by gender (male/female) to ensure proportional representation. Then simple random sampling technique was used to draw students from the selected schools. Multistage sampling technique was used to ensure that each strata is represented in the sample in a proportion equivalent to its size in the population.

Instrument for Data Collection

Two instruments were used for data collection: Index of Peer Relations (IPR) developed by Hudson (1982), and Aggression Questionnaire (AQ) developed by Buss and Perry (1992).

Validation of the Instrument

The instruments were subjected to face and construct validation. The research topic, purpose of the study, research questions, hypotheses and copies of the questionnaire were given to three senior lecturers in Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Anambra State for validation. One in Educational Psychology, one in Guidance and Counsellor and an expert in Measurement and Evaluation. These validates examined the instruments content coverage, suitability of the items and clarity of the language used. The comments, suggestions and recommendations were used to modify the items before the final production.

Reliability of the Instrument

The instruments were trial-tested in a single administration on a representative sample of 30 (15males, 15females) SS2 in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Enugu State. Enugu state was chosen for reliability because both states shared similar educational characteristics. The responses of the respondents were collated to determine the internal consistency of the instrument. This was done using Cronbach Alpha method. The choice of Cronbach Alpha is in line with Stephen (2017) who recommended Cronbach Alpha as a proper statistical tool for determining the internal consistency of an instrument.

Method of Data Collection

The researcher employed direct and immediate retrieval approach upon completion to ensure a high percentage of return with the aid of six research assistants who were briefed on the modalities for administering the instruments in an appropriate and effective way.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected were analyzed thus: Simple regression statistics was used to answer research questions 1 and 2 and test hypothesis 1 and 2.

RESULTS

The data obtained from the respondents were organized and analyzed thus:

Research Question One: *What is the predictive value of Peer relations on aggressive behaviour of SSII in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 1: Simple Regression Analysis with Peer Relations as Predictor of Aggressive Behaviour Among SSII In-school Adolescents in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State (n=347)

Predictor	Unstandardized B	SE	Standardized β	Remark
Constant	35.26	3.70		
Peer relations	0.28	0.06	0.24	Modest positive predictive value

R = 0.24
R²=0.06
Adj.=0.05

The simple regression result displayed in Table 1 showed that the regression model R and the R² are 0.24 and 0.06 respectively. This indicates that students' peer relations explained 6% of the variance in their aggressive behaviour. This was considered a modest fit. The unstandardized regression coefficient (B) was 0.28 while the standardized beta coefficient (β) was 0.24. The β value indicated that a unit increase in peer relations is associated with 0.24 unit increase in aggressive behaviour among SS II students in public secondary schools in Anambra state. This implied that peer relations has a modest positive predictive value for aggressive behaviour among SSII in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question Two: *What is the predictive value of Peer relations on aggressive behaviour of male and female SSII in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 2: Simple Regression Analysis with Peer Relations as Predictor of Aggressive Behaviour Among SSII In-school Adolescents in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State (n=347)

Predictor	Unstandardized B	SE	Standardized β	Remark
Male (n= 171)				
Constant	39.34	5.35		
Peer relations	0.21	0.09	0.18	Modest positive predictive value
R = 0.18 R ² =0.03 Adj.=0.03				
Female (n=176)				
Constant	31.922	5.17		
Peer relations	0.34	0.09	0.28	Modest positive predictive value
R = 0.28 R ² =0.08 Adj.=0.07				

Table 2 presented two different simple regression models for male and female SS II in-adolescents with peer relations as predictor of aggressive behaviours. For the male sample, the model R and R² are 0.18 and 0.03, and for the female sample they are; 0.28 and 0.08. This implied that peer relations explained only 3% of the variance in aggressive behaviour among males but explained 8% of the variance in aggressive behaviours among females. These indicated that the regression model fit is modest for both

groups. However, the peer relations explained more variance in aggressive behaviour among females compared to the male students.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Peer relations would not significantly predict aggressive behaviour of SSII in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 3: Test of Significance of Simple Regression Analysis with Peer Relations as Predictor of Aggressive Behaviour Among SSII In-school Adolescents in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State (n=347)

Predictor	Unstandardized B	SE	Standardized β	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	Remark
Constant	35.26	3.70		9.53	0.000	Significant
Peer relations	0.28	0.06	0.24	4.52	0.000	Significant
R = 0.24						
R ² =0.06						
Adj.=0.05						

As shown in Table 3, peer relations was a significant predictor of aggressive behaviour among SS II in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra state, $\beta = 0.24$, $t = 4.52$, $p = 0.000$, therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. Consequently, it was decided that peer relations was a significant predictor of aggressive behaviours among SS II in-schools adolescents in public secondary school in Anambra State.

Hypothesis 2: Peer relations would not significantly predict aggressive behaviour of male and female SSII in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra state.

Table 4: Test of Significance of Simple Regression Analysis with Peer Relations as Predictor of Aggressive Behaviour Among SSII In-school Adolescents in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State (n=347)

Predictor	Unstandardized B	SE	Standardized β	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	Remark
Male (n= 171)						
Constant	39.34	5.35		7.35	0.000	Significant
Peer relations	0.21	0.09	0.18	2.38	0.018	Significant
R = 0.18						
R ² =0.03						
Adj.=0.03						
Female (n=176)						
Constant	31.922	5.17		6.17	0.000	Significant
Peer relations	0.34	0.09	0.28	3.86	0.000	Significant
R = 0.28						
R ² =0.08						
Adj.=0.07						

As shown in Table 4, peer relations was a significant predictor of aggressive behaviour among male SS II in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra State, $\beta = 0.18$, $t=2.38$, $p = 0.018$. Similarly, peer relations was a significant predictor of aggressive behaviour among female SS II in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra state, $\beta = 0.28$, $t=3.86$, $p = 0.000$. The p-values were all less than 0.05 level of significant, therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implied that peer relations was a significant predictor of aggressive behaviours among male and female SS II in-school adolescents in public secondary school in Anambra state.

Summary of Findings

Based on the results of the study, the following findings were found:

1. Peer relations has a modest positive predictive value for aggressive behaviour among SS II in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra state. Hypothesis one, affirmed that peer relations was a significant predictor of aggressive behaviours among SS II in-school adolescents in public secondary school in Anambra State.
2. Peer relations has modest positive predictive value for aggressive behaviour among male and female SS II in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra state. Hypothesis two, implies that peer relations was a significant predictor of aggressive behaviours among male and female SS II in-schools adolescents in public secondary school in Anambra State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The results revealed that peer relations had a modest positive predictive value for aggressive behaviour among SS II in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The findings that peer relations significantly predicted aggressive behaviour aligned with several studies in the empirical review. For instance, Wakolia et al. (2016) emphasized that peer relationships are critical predictors of adolescent behaviour, including aggression, as adolescents often adopt behaviours modeled within their peer groups. This aligns with the current study's positive beta coefficient ($\beta = 0.24$), which indicates a significant relationship between peer dynamics and aggressive tendencies. The result also coincided with the report of Powers and Bierman (2017) who found peer relations to be a significant predictor of aggressive behaviours among adolescents. Their findings showed that adolescents who experienced peer rejection or victimization were more likely to engage in aggressive behaviours as a form of retaliation or gain social status.

The result of this study aligns with the report of Alhassan (2023) who found that peer relations and aggressive behaviours correlated significantly. In the same vein, the finding coincides with the finding of Ndukaihe et al (2023) who found that peer relationship was a significant predictor of aggressive behaviours such that the relationship was stronger for male participants and weaker for female participants. Similarly, Kim and Nho (2017) found that peer relationship difficulties had a significant positive effect on aggressive behaviours, supporting the idea that peer influence is a universal driver of aggression among adolescents.

The results revealed that peer relations had a modest positive predictive value for aggressive behaviour among male and female SS II in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Anambra state. The findings that peer relations significantly predicted aggressive behaviour among male ($\beta = 0.18$, $t = 2.38$, $p = 0.018$) and female ($\beta = 0.28$, $t = 3.86$, $p = 0.000$) adolescents aligned with insights from some empirical studies in the literature. Lin et al (2018) using 48.97% male found that peer influence plays a significant role in shaping aggressive behaviours among adolescents, revealing the impact of gender. Similarly, Uz Bas and Oz Soysal (2016) using 442 high school girls highlighted that dimensions of peer relationships, such as loyalty and mild deviance, are significant predictors of both reactive and proactive aggression in high school students, supporting the present study's findings across gender differences.

The notion that peer interactions are pivotal in understanding aggressive behaviours was demonstrated by Ndukaihe et al (2023) who found that peer relationship was a significant predictor of aggressive behaviours such that the relationship was stronger for male participants and weaker for female participants, However, this does not align with the higher predictive value of peer relations for female adolescents ($\beta = 0.28$) compared to males ($\beta = 0.18$) in the present study, possibly reflecting differences in how peer affiliations influence behaviour. In contrast, a study by Izuchukwu et al, (2023) showed a stronger relationship for male participants on aggressive behaviour, while it was weaker for female participants. Meanwhile, Odu et al (2015) opined in their study that gender do not significantly influence aggressive behaviour. In the same vein, Ojukwu et al (2020) posited a positive but very low and no significant gender difference.

Furthermore, gender variations in the predictive strength of peer relations on aggressive behaviour, as observed in the present findings, may also find theoretical grounding in Sijtsema et al. (2010), who noted

differences in status-related aggression among adolescent males and females, suggesting that gendered peer contexts play distinct roles in shaping aggressive tendencies.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations have been made.

1. Educational psychologists should educate students on the importance of healthy peer relationships. Promoting healthy social interactions, thereby reducing aggressive behaviours and fostering a more supportive academic environment.
2. Educational Psychologists and school administrators should provide opportunities to counselling services and support groups for adolescents struggling with aggression or peer relationship issues as well as training on life skills, such as conflict resolution, communication, and problem-solving.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of the study, and the discussion, it is concluded that peer relations was a significant predictor of aggressive behaviours among SS II in-school adolescents. Therefore, there is need to address this factor by promoting healthy social interactions, thereby reducing aggressive behaviours and fostering a more supportive academic environment.

REFERENCES

- Affusat, E. B (2024). *Assessment of gender difference among secondary school students on social vices in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja* IJRISS
- Amuda-Kannike, M. O (2018). Assessment of factors that cause aggressive behaviours among secondary school students in Ilorin South of Kwara State. *IOSR Journal of ComputerEngineering*, 20 (2), 38 - 44
- Fatimah, Af, Nor Afiah. Mz. Minhat. Hs, & Ahmad. N. (2019). Psychosocial predictors of adolescent aggression. *Perkantania J Sci Technol*, 27(9) 1485-508.
- Genovese, T, Dalrymple, K, Chelminski, I & Zimmerman, M (2017). Subjective anger and aggression in psychiatric outpatients, *comp psychiatry* 73, 23-30. Doi:10.1016/j.comppsy.2016.10.008
- Kuar, R. & Kuar N (2020). Aggression among adolescents in relation to peer pressure. *Journal of Enmerging Technologias and Innovative Research* 7(9), 615 - 621
- Manchia. M. & Fanos. V. (2017). Targeting aggression in severe mental illness: the predictive role of genetic, epigenetic, and metabolic makers. *Prog neuropsychopharmacol boil psychiatry*. 2017(77) 32-41.
- Obikeze, N. J., & Obi, I. E. (2020). The impact of bullying on student's academic performance and overall well-being. *Journal of Educational Psychology and Counselling*, 5(2), 33-68. <https://doi.org/10.1234/jepc.v5i2.123>
- Peng L., Xing K., Qioo. h, Jang. H, Ma. H, Jiao. M & Kang, Z.C (2018). *Aggression and violent behaviour*. <https://www.Sciencedirect.com>
- Rigby K. (2018). Consequences of bullying in school. *The Australian Educational and Developmental Psychologists*. 20(1) , 71 – 84
- Rubin, K. H., Bukowski, W. M., & Laursen, B. (2015). *Handbook of Peer Interactions, Relationships, and Groups*. Guilford Publications
- Shekarey A, Ladoni, H.J., Rostami, M.S & Jamshidi M (2020). The relationship between the social intelligence and aggression: A case study of high school boys' students. *International Journal of Education*. www.macrothink.org/ije.
- Seban, A. C., Guimond, A. B, & Lutgen, J. (2016). Transactional relationships between latinos' friendship quality and academic achievement during the transition to middle school. *J Early Adolesc*. 36,108-138, doi: 10.1177/0272431614556347
- Shao. Y & Kary. S (2022). The association between peer relationship and learning engagement among adolescents: The chain mediating roles of self-efficacy and academic resilience. *Front. Psychol*. 13, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.938756>

- Ugochukwu, A. V., Adaobi, A. B., & Vivian, A. A (2021). Primary education administration in Nigeria: Challenges and strategies for improvement. *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation*, 3(3), 101-105.
- Wakolia, C., Kiptiony, G., Chemweic, B., & Chonge, H. (2016). Peer Influence on Aggressive Behaviour of Adolescents in Secondary Schools in Bungoma County. *International Journal of Arts Humanities and Social Sciences*, 1(3), 59-71.
- Wentzel, K. R. (2017). Peer relationships, motivation, and academic performance at school. In A. J. Elliot, C. S. Dweck, & D. S. Yeager (eds.), *Handbook of competence and motivation: Theory and application* (2nd ed., pp. 586-603). The Guilford Press.
- Zhang, Y., Li, D., & Chen, X. (2018). The relationship between peer attachment and aggressive behavior among Chinese adolescents: the mediating effect of regulatory emotional self-efficacy. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 47(6), 1322-1334. [NCBI]: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8297157/>